

THE INFLUENCE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND EMPLOYEE EMPOWERMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT THROUGH JOB SATISFACTION AT SOCIAL SERVICE SPECIAL REGION OF YOGYAKARTA

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Abstract

The research was purposed to find out whether there was any significant of emotional intelligence and employee empowerment to organizational commitment through job satisfaction on Social Service in Special Region of Yogyakarta. The participants of this research are the employees of Social Service in Special Region of Yogyakarta. Quantitative approach was used during data collection which 107 employees had been participated. This study was using SmartPLS 3.0 version to test the hypothesis. The results of this study found that there are significant positive effect of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment, significant positive effect of employee's empowerment on organizational commitment, significant positive effect of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction, and significant positive effect of organizational commitment on job satisfaction, also there is significant positive effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment. In addition, this study found the direct influence of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment is greater than indirect influence of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment through job satisfaction, and the direct influence of employee empowerment on organizational commitment is greater than indirect influence of employee empowerment on organizational commitment through job satisfaction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One important component in an organization is the human resources that are in it. Mathis & Jackson (2011), states that human resources are a special part of each organization, which means that the organization must be able to see the talent of an employee to improve employee performance and as an opportunity to create a greater competitive advantage of the organization. In addition, Bohlander & Snell (2001), states that human resources are integrated capabilities of the power of thought and physical power that each individual has built to be able to compete in the face of increasingly fierce competition.

Organizational commitment is generally defined as the identification and involvement of someone who is relatively strong towards an organization. Organizational commitment has been widely associated with several variables of research by researchers, such as with professional commitment variables, organizational citizenship behavior (Bogler & Somech 2004), job satisfaction, perceived organizational justice (Karim & Rehman 2012), Teamwork, Employee Training (Hanaysha 2016) and occupational stress (Aghdasi Kiamanesh & Ebrahim 2011). Therefore, to increase the organizational commitment of employees, there are several factors that influence it such as emotional intelligence possessed by employees, employee empowerment provided by the organization, and employee job satisfaction on the work performed.

The first factor that influences organizational commitment is emotional intelligence. Goleman (in Armstrong & Taylor, 2014) defines emotional intelligence as the capacity to recognize one's own feelings and feelings towards others, to motivate yourself and process one's own emotions in relation to others. Furthermore Goleman (2003), revealed that emotional intelligence has the same efficacy as intellectual intelligence, and sometimes effective in intellectual intelligence, this is confirmed that intellectual intelligence only contributes 20% to

one's success, while another 80% is determined by other factors, then it is undeniable that emotional intelligence is very important and able to influence employee organizational commitment

The second factor that influences organizational commitment is employee empowerment. Herzberg, et al (1959), stated that employee empowerment is an autonomy of work and enrichment focused on improving control and decision making in one's work. Meanwhile, Yulk in Supriyanto (2009) stated that employee empowerment is intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy of people who are influenced by leadership behavior, job characteristics, organizational structure, and their own needs and values.

The third factor that influences organizational commitment is job satisfaction. Armstrong and Taylor (2014), state that job satisfaction is a person's behavior and feelings towards the work they have. Thus employee productivity can be improved by making employees in the organization feel more satisfied, because it is empowered by the organization and the social needs of an employee feel fulfilled.

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee empowerment of organizational commitment and job satisfaction. This research is unique because it tries to analyze the four variables (emotional intelligence, employee empowerment, organizational commitment, job satisfaction) in one research model. This research is also unique because it incorporates employee empowerment variables into the research model. Because, employee empowerment is still rare in previous studies.

2. THEORY FOUNDATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis Development

Relationship of Emotional Intelligence with Organizational Commitment

The results of this study are in accordance with previous studies of Shafiq and Rana (2016), who found that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant relationship influence on organizational commitment. Likewise with research conducted by Alavi et al., (2013), which states that there is a positive influence of emotional intelligence with organizational commitment
H1: emotional intelligence has a positive influence on organizational commitment

Relationship of Employee Empowerment with Organizational Commitment

The results of this study are in accordance with Hanaysha's previous studies (2016), which states that there is a positive influence made by empowering employees on organizational commitment. This result is similar to previous research conducted by Goundarzavand and Kheradmand (2013), which revealed a positive and significant influence between employee empowerment and organizational commitment.

H2: employee empowerment has a positive influence on organizational commitment

Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Commitment Mediated by Job Satisfaction

Emotional intelligence is known to have a positive relationship to job satisfaction (Elias at al 2012, Seyal and Afzaal 2013, Badawy and Magdy 2015), and job satisfaction has a positive influence on organizational commitment (Auda 2016, Azeem and Akhtar 2014, Aghdasi, Gangai and Agrawal 2015).

H3: Job satisfaction will mediate the relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational commitment

Relationship of Employee Empowerment with Organizational Commitment Mediated by Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction has been found to have a mediating effect (Gulleryuz et al 2008). In his research job satisfaction can mediate the relationship between employee empowerment,

emotional intelligence, and organizational commitment. In addition, research conducted by Goundarzavand and Kheradmand (2013), describes the existence of a positive relationship between employee empowerment and organizational commitment.

H4: Job satisfaction will mediate the relationship between employee empowerment and organizational commitment

Theoretical Basis

Emotional Intelligence

Goleman (1990), defines that emotional intelligence as the ability to recognize one's own feelings and feelings of others, in motivating yourself and managing emotions well to yourself and in relationships related to yourself. Meanwhile, according to Davies in Auda (2016), states the definition of emotional intelligence as a good ability in understanding emotions in yourself and reading the emotions of others. Mayer (1990), in Goleman (2007), reveals that there are two sides of emotional intelligence, namely the first is intelligence in understanding emotional and adding creativity, and the second is intuition in the logical mind.

Employee Empowerment

Snell and Bohlander (2013), reveal that empowerment is a process of giving strength to employees to be able to initiate change, thereby encouraging them to take responsibility for what they do. Employee empowerment is now a trend of managing human capital in organizations in the future (Mulyadi, 2007). Furthermore Herzberg, et al (1959), stated that employee empowerment is an autonomy of work and enrichment that is focused on improving control and decision making in one's work.

Organizational Commitment

According to Robbins (2008), organizational commitment is a situation where an employee will side with a particular organization and has a goal and desire to remain a member of the organization. Meanwhile, according to Porter et al., (1974), defining organizational commitment is the desire to remain dependent on the value of the organization, strive to follow these values, and the desire to always be part of the organization.

Job satisfaction

Gibson et al (2012), said that job satisfaction is an individual behavior related to his work, and job satisfaction is also a perception of work related to environmental factors such as supervisor's leadership style, procedures, regulations, relationship of a group, work conditions, and tunjangan. Meanwhile, Spector (2000), defines job satisfaction as an attitude that reflects how a person feels about his work as a whole or on various aspects of his work.

Operational Definition of Research Variables

Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman (2003), there are several dimensions and indicators in emotional intelligence, namely: Self Awareness, Self regulation, Self Motivation, Empathy, Social skill.

Employee Empowerment

Indicators of employee empowerment measurement in this study refer to the parameters made by Khan (1997), namely: desire, trust, confident, credibility, accountability, communication.

Organizational Commitment

The indicator of organizational commitment measurement in this study refers to the parameters made by (Allen and Meyer, 1990), namely: affective commitment, continuen commitment, normative commitment.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction indicators, including: promotion, supervision, co-workers, nature of work, conditions of work, operational conditions, communication, salary, contingency rewards, awards.

3. Research Sample

This research was conducted on employees of PNS in the social service of the Special Region of Yogyakarta. There were 125 questionnaires distributed with a return of 107 questionnaires.

Data Analysis Technique

1) Model Conceptualization

Model conceptualization is the first step in PLS - SEM analysis. At this stage researchers must develop and measure constructs.

2) Determine the Algorithm Analysis Method

In PLS-SEM using the SmartPLS 3.0 program, the algorithm analysis method provided is only PLS algorithm with three schema choices, namely, factorial, centroid, and path or structural weighting. The recommended PLS algorithm scheme is path or structural weighting.

3) Determine the Resampling Method

Generally, there are two resampling methods used by researchers in the SEM field to carry out the re-sampling process, namely the bootstrapping and jackknifing methods. In this study, a bootstrapping method is used, which is a method that uses all original samples to re-sample. This method is more often used in structural equation models.

4) Draw Path Diagrams

After conceptualizing the model, determining the method of algorithm analysis and resampling methods, the next step is to draw a path diagram of the model to be estimated. In drawing a path diagram.

5) Model Evaluation

After drawing a path diagram, the model is ready to be estimated and the overall results are evaluated. Model evaluation in PLS - SEM using the SmartPLS 3.0 program

5. DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model Measurement

Second Order Confirmatory Analysis

Second order confirmatory analysis is the theoretical relationship between latent variables or high order constructs with the construct dimension below them (Jogiyanto, 2011)

Table1. Path Coefficient Measurement of SCFA Significance

Konstruk	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
AC -> PMBDKY	0.189	0.190	0.023	8.287	0.000
COM -> PMBDKY	0.200	0.198	0.024	8.350	0.000
CON -> PMBDKY	0.263	0.259	0.027	9.571	0.000
CR -> PMBDKY	0.211	0.210	0.023	9.253	0.000
DE -> PMBDKY	0.250	0.252	0.036	7.003	0.000
EM -> KCEM	0.358	0.357	0.036	9.830	0.000
GA -> KPSKJ	0.104	0.103	0.021	5.069	0.000
IK -> KPSKJ	0.171	0.170	0.024	7.249	0.000
KA -> KMORG	0.503	0.503	0.043	11.729	0.000

KKN -> KMORG	0.384	0.378	0.044	8.643	0.000
KN -> KMORG	0.345	0.343	0.027	12.892	0.000
KOM -> KPSKJ	0.224	0.222	0.027	8.282	0.000
KOP -> KPSKJ	0.067	0.069	0.017	3.967	0.000
PE -> KPSKJ	0.235	0.233	0.024	9.843	0.000
PR -> KPSKJ	0.063	0.060	0.033	1.908	0.000
RK -> KPSKJ	0.156	0.155	0.023	6.780	0.000
SA -> KCEM	0.222	0.221	0.035	6.276	0.000
SM -> KCEM	0.272	0.271	0.035	7.878	0.000
SP -> KPSKJ	0.146	0.148	0.023	6.472	0.000
SR -> KCEM	0.310	0.306	0.034	9.037	0.000
SS -> KCEM	0.187	0.185	0.030	6.291	0.000
SU -> KPSKJ	0.206	0.200	0.030	6.786	0.000
TR -> PMBDKY	0.192	0.193	0.021	8.968	0.000

Based on the results of the path coefficient contained in the table above shows that all items are significant to the construct with t-statistics > 1.96 and p-values < 0.05. Thus it can be stated that the indicators EM, SA, SM, SR, SS are construct forming variables of Emotional Intelligence (KCEM), indicators AC, COM, CON, CR, DE, TR are manifest variables forming the construct of Employee Empowerment (PMBDKY), indicators GA, IK, KOM, KOP, PE, PR, RK, SP, SU are manifest variables forming the construct of Job Satisfaction (KPSKJ), then the indicator of train, KKN, KN is a manifest variable constructing the Organizational Commitment (KMORG).

Mediation Effect Testing

The first stage

The first step in testing the mediating effect is to examine the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables and must be significant in the t-statistic value > 1.96

Table 2. First Stage Testing Coefficient Path

Konstruk	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)
KCEM -> KMORG	0.273	0.291	0.084	3.233
PMBDKY -> KMORG	0.425	0.444	0.096	4.431

Second Stage

At this stage, testing the significance of the exogenous variables on the mediating variable is carried out and must be significant in the t-statistic value > 1.96.

Table 3. Second Stage Testing Coefficient Path

Konstruk	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)
KCEM -> KPSKJ	0.331	0.346	0.113	2.915
PMBDKY -> KPSKJ	0.310	0.349	0.101	3.074

Third phase

At this stage, simultaneous testing of exogenous variables of training satisfaction, psychological empowerment and mediating work engagement variables towards endogenous turnover intention variables was conducted.

Table 4. Total Effect

Konstruk	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)
KCEM -> KMORG	0.260	0.275	0.089	2.909
KCEM -> KPSKJ	0.320	0.329	0.123	2.610
KPSKJ -> KMORG	0.227	0.227	0.100	2.261
PMBDKY -> KMORG	0.423	0.438	0.101	4.201
PMBDKY -> KPSKJ	0.301	0.323	0.115	2.623

To find out how far the variable job satisfaction can analyze the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee empowerment of organizational commitment can be seen in the table specific indirect effects. It can be seen from the table that the relationship of emotional intelligence to organizational commitment mediated by job satisfaction is still significant with a t-statistic value of 2.810 < 1.96, this means that job satisfaction acts as a partial control. and indirect (Garson, 2016). Likewise, the relationship of employee empowerment to organizational commitment mediated by job satisfaction is still significant with a t-statistic of 2,376 > 1.96, this also means that job satisfaction acts as a partial control in the relationship between employee empowerment and organizational commitment.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Organizational Commitment

Exogenous constructs of emotional intelligence have a significant positive effect (O = 0.188) with the construct of organizational commitment. The t-statistic value in this construct relationship is 2014 > 1.96, and the p-value is 0.044 < 0.05. Therefore, the first hypothesis which states that emotional intelligence has a positive influence on organizational commitment is proven to be true.

Effect of Employee Empowerment on Organizational Commitment

Exogenous construction of employee empowerment has a significant positive effect (O = 0.355) with the construct of organizational commitment. The t-statistic value in this construct relationship is 3,086 > 1.96, and the p-value is 0.002 < 0.05. Therefore, the second hypothesis stating that employee empowerment has a positive influence on organizational commitment is proven to be true.

The Mediation Effect of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Commitment

From the results of the PLS analysis above, it was found that emotional intelligence has a significant positive influence (O = 0.260) on organizational commitment with a t-statistic value of 2.909 > 1.96. Emotional intelligence has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction (O = 0.320) with a t-statistic value of 2.610 > 1.96. Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect (O = 0.227) on organizational commitment with a t-statistical value of 2,261 > 1.96. Therefore, the sixth hypothesis states that job satisfaction will mediate the relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational commitment proven to be true.

The Mediation Effect of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Employee Empowerment and Organizational Commitment

From the results of the PLS analysis above, it was found that employee empowerment has a significant positive effect ($O = 0.423$) on organizational commitment with a t-statistic value of $4,201 > 1.96$. Employee empowerment has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction ($O = 0.301$) with a t-statistic value of $2.623 > 1.96$. Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect ($O = 0.227$) on organizational commitment with a t-statistical value of $2,261 > 1.96$. Therefore, the seventh hypothesis which states that job satisfaction will mediate the relationship between employee empowerment and organizational commitment is proven to be true.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion of the influence of emotional intelligence and employee empowerment on organizational commitment through job satisfaction in the Yogyakarta Special District Social Service, some conclusions can be given as follows:

1. There is a significant positive effect between emotional intelligence on organizational commitment as evidenced by the significance value of the t-statistic value in this relationship is $2014 > 1.96$, and the p-value of $0.044 < 0.05$.
2. There is a significant positive influence between employee empowerment on organizational commitment as evidenced by the significance value of the t-statistic value in this construct relationship is $3.086 > 1.96$, and the p value - value $0.002 < 0.05$.
3. There is an indirect influence of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment through job satisfaction as evidenced by the significance value of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment with a t-statistic value of $2.909 > 1.96$. Then, the significance value of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction with a t-statistic value of $2.610 > 1.96$. Meanwhile, the significance value of job satisfaction on organizational commitment with a t-statistic value of $2,261 > 1.96$. So based on the significance value of each path, it is stated that there is an indirect influence of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment through job satisfaction.
4. There is an indirect effect of employee empowerment on organizational commitment through job satisfaction as evidenced by the significance value of employee empowerment of organizational commitment with a t-statistic value of $4,201 > 1.96$. Then, the significance value of employee empowerment on job satisfaction with a t-statistic value of $2.623 > 1.96$. Meanwhile, the significance value of job satisfaction on organizational commitment with a t-statistic value of $2,261 > 1.96$. So based on the significance value of each path, it is stated that there is an indirect effect of employee empowerment on organizational commitment through job satisfaction.

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